

CONSENT FORM

Study Title: Beyond Push–Pull: Emotional Ambivalence and Digital Networks in Nigerian Teachers' Migration Intentions

Participant Consent Statements

Please read each statement carefully and tick where appropriate:

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet for this study.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw at any time before data analysis begins without giving any reason.
- I understand that the interview will be audio-recorded for transcription purposes only.
- I understand that all information I provide will be treated confidentially and that my identity will not be disclosed in any publication or report.
- I understand that anonymised data from this study may be stored securely for research purposes for up to five years after publication, in line with the University of Johannesburg's research data retention policy.
- I understand that my raw interview data will not be shared publicly or deposited in any open repository, in line with POPIA and the University of Johannesburg's data protection policies.
- I agree to take part in this research study.

Signature Section

Participant Name: _____

Participant Signature: _____

Date: _____

Principal Researcher's Name: Chidubem Deborah Adamu

Principal Researcher's Signature:

Date: 22/09/2025